

Chemical Engineering: An International Journal (CEIJ)

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Scope

Chemical Engineering: An International Journal (CEIJ) is a Quarterly peer-reviewed and refereed open access journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of Chemical Engineering. The journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on theoretical and practical aspects of Chemical Engineering research.

The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on Chemical Engineering research advancements, and establishing new collaborations in these areas. Original research papers, state-of-the-art reviews are invited for publication in all areas of Chemical Engineering.

Topics of interest include but are not limited to, the following :

- Biotechnology and Bio-Systems Engineering
- Catalysis and Reaction Engineering
- Energy
- Environment
- Materials Engineering / Nanotechnology /Polymer
- Process Systems Engineering
- Transport, Colloids, and Interface Science

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through [Submission System](#). Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal. For paper format download the template in this page

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : December 13, 2024**
- Notification : January 13, 2025
- Final Manuscript Due : January 20, 2025
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : cejournals@airccse.com or cej@airconline.com

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